

DETERMINING THE OPTIMAL PARAMETERS OF THE HYDROCOOLING PROCESS FOR THE STORAGE OF FRESH JUJUBE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20770065>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 16th June 2026

Accepted: 18th June 2026

Online: 20th June 2026

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the results of a study on the use of hydrocooling to preserve the freshness of jujube fruits in cold storage conditions, thereby extending the shelf life of the fruits and preserving their quality indicators to the maximum. Experiments were conducted to determine the optimal water temperature during the hydrocooling process at temperatures of +1, +3, +5 and to determine the duration of the treatment in various combinations of 5, 15, 25 minutes.

During the storage period of jujube fruits, a significant degree of natural shrinkage and fruit shrinkage was observed, which was influenced by storage temperature and storage time. As the storage period increased, natural shrinkage increased from 5-41% at all three storage temperatures and the proportion of shriveled fruits increased from 6-60%. The lowest proportion of natural shrinkage and shriveled fruits was observed when stored in a cold storage with a low temperature of 5 °C, followed by a cold storage with an average temperature of 15 °C, and the highest proportion was observed at normal room temperature (22 °C) [1].

Introduction. During the storage period, a significant natural shrinkage and shriveling of the fruits were observed, which was influenced by storage temperature and shelf life. As the shelf life increases, at all three storage temperatures, the natural loss increases by 5–41%, and the proportion of shriveled fruits increases by 6–60%. The smallest proportion of natural shrinkage and shrivelled fruits was observed when stored in cold storage at a low temperature of 5 °C, followed by a cold storage at a moderate temperature of 15 °C, and the highest proportion was observed at normal room temperature (22 °C). [1].

The timing of the ripening of Jujube fruits is considered one of the critical technological processes that must be taken into account during storage and processing. Fruits consumed

fresh should be harvested at the beginning of the technical ripening period, when the fruits are just beginning to color[2].

The main task of storage is not only to help reduce natural loss and damage of the product, but also to ensure the preservation of the commercial condition of the grapes and their condition that meets consumer demand, preventing the development of various microorganisms by creating an optimal regime of temperature, humidity, and composition in the warehouse, and slowing down processes that lead to the deterioration of the product's quality properties[3].

Experimental results and discussion. After harvesting the fruits, the rapid removal of the accumulated field heat is considered one of the crucial stages of the storage process. One of the effective methods used for this purpose is hydro-culling technology. Hydrocooling is a method of rapid cooling of the product using cold water (0-5°C), allowing for the reduction of fruit temperature to the optimal level in a short period of time. Compared to other precoiling methods, the cooling process proceeds much faster due to the higher thermal conductivity of water.

The theoretical foundations of applying hydrocooling technology to jujube fruits are explained by the physiological mechanism of this method's action. As a result of cooling, the intensity of respiration decreases, the synthesis and effect of ethylene decrease, the stability of cell membranes is maintained, and the rate of water loss decreases. This allows for the long-term preservation of the hardness, color, and flavor characteristics of the fruits.

Hydrocooling technology is considered one of the promising methods for rapid cooling of jujube fruits after harvesting, and expanding research on determining optimal parameters for jujube fruits and evaluating its effectiveness is scientifically and practically relevant.

Using this method, experiments were conducted to determine the effect of jujube fruits on reducing metabolic activity and extending shelf life. Among the 10 unubu varieties used as the object of our research, the "Linyulizao" variety was selected, the fruit hardness was 80-120 kg/cm², and the processes were carried out according to the table indicators (Table 1).

According to the data presented in the table, the "Linyulizao" jujube variety underwent hydrocooling in water at a temperature of 1°C for various periods of 5, 15, and 25 minutes. If we analyze the results, the most effective result was recorded in the 15 and 25-minute treatment variants; that is, the mass loss was the same at 3.9%, and the fruit hardness was the same at 88%, but there was a slight difference of 1 day between the shelf life, which was 26-29 and 27-30 days, respectively.

Mass in the subsequent 5-minute hydrocooling variant. losses were 5.6%, fruit hardness was 80%, and shelf life was 21-24 days. However, in the control variant, mass loss was 14.3%, fruit hardness was 80%, and the shelf life was 8-10 days, which is almost 2 times lower than the overall indicators of all other variants and is assessed as unsatisfactory.

Experiments were also conducted at a temperature of 3°C for the same indicators; the shelf life of the fruits ranged from 18 to 26 days, mass loss was 4.9–5.8%, and fruit hardness was 78–85%. Although the highest indicators in this experiment belonged to the 15 and 25-minute treatment method, all three variants were evaluated with a good overall score.

In this variant, where hydrocooling was performed at a temperature of 5°C for 5, 15, and 25 minutes, the fruit shelf life was 16–21 days, mass loss was 4.6–4.9%, and fruit hardness

ranged from 76 to 80%. In this experiment, the highest indicator belonged to the 15 and 25-minute treatment methods; compared to the control, the mass loss was 9.7% lower, and the shelf life was increased by 11 days.

Table 1

Efficiency of applying hydrocooling technology in the storage of jujube fruits in cold storage conditions

N ^o	Group	Method	Water temperature (°C)	Processing time (minutes)	Loss of mass (%)	Fruit hardness (%)	Storage period (days)	Total grade
1	N-1 (Control)	without cooling	+22	—	14.3 ± 1.2	47	8 – 10	Not satisfied
2	G-1	hydrocooling	+1	5	5.6 ± 0.4	80	21 – 24	Good
3	G-2	hydrocooling	+1	15	3.9 ± 0.3	88	26 – 29	Excellent
4	G-3	hydrocooling	+1	25	3.9 ± 0.3	88	27 – 30	Excellent
5	G-4	hydrocooling	+3	5	5.8 ± 0.4	78	18 – 21	Good
6	G-5	hydrocooling	+3	15	4.9 ± 0.3	85	21 – 25	Good
7	G-6	hydrocooling	+3	25	4.9 ± 0.3	85	21 – 26	Good
8	G-7	hydrocooling	+5	5	4.9 ± 0.4	76	16 – 19	Good
9	G-8	hydrocooling	+5	15	4.6 ± 0.3	79	19 – 21	Good
10	G-9	hydrocooling	+5	25	4.6 ± 0.3	80	20 – 21	Good

Conclusion

The most effective results were recorded in the 15 and 25-minute treatment variants; i.e., the mass loss was the same at 3.9%, and the fruit hardness was similar at 88%, but there was a slight 1-day difference between the shelf life, which was 26-29 and 27-30 days, respectively. Taking into account the low consumption of water and energy from an economic point of view, it is recommended to treat with 15-minute hydro-culling as the most optimal method.

It was also proven that the hydrocooling regimen is the most optimal, noting that fruits undergoing hydrocooling are stored significantly longer than in the control group and have higher quality indicators.

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